

NEWSLETTER

Welcome to CONCILIARE: Advancing Our Research

Welcome to the fifth edition of the CONCILIARE Newsletter!

Dear colleagues, as our project progresses, we are pleased to share updates on our activities, upcoming events, and new resources. This newsletter aims to serve as a platform to promote the project's activities, parallel events, and ongoing research, keeping partners and collaborators informed and connected.

NEWS

New Publication on Collective Memory and Intergroup Relations

On 13 August 2025, an article co-authored by Maria Babińska and Laurent Licata was published in *Current Opinion in Psychology*. The paper presents an analysis of how majority and minority group members construe collective history, and how institutions can either reinforce or help bridge intergroup inequalities.

Babińska, M., & Licata, L. (2025). Mnemonic asymmetries: How collective memory shapes and reflects intergroup relations. *Current Opinion in Psychology*, 102150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copsy.2025.102150>

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Associated Partners of CONCILIARE

After the amendment to the Grant agreement of CONCILIARE (AMENDMENT No AMD-101132582-3) the two museums that were collaborating with us, became officially associated partners: the Royal Museum for Central Africa in Tervuren (Belgium) and the African Museum (Fondazione Nigrizia Onlus) in Verona (Italy).

CONCILIARE integrates EU-funded project cluster

CONCILIARE was selected to integrate a clustering opportunity with 3 other projects funded by the European Commission. The activation of Booster Service 3.2, organized by Francesco Ghini (Communication and Dissemination Senior Officer/Booster Services Expert) aims at supporting the creation of the cluster, identify shared challenges or solutions and define common key exploitable results to be jointly disseminated.

Open Science & Podcasts: CONCILIARE researchers in dialogue

As part of its commitment to open science and public engagement, CONCILIARE researchers have recently contributed to two podcasts.

- Laurent Licata participated in *Milgram des savoirs* (Université libre de Bruxelles), in an episode dedicated to psychology and collective memory.
🔊 Listen here: [Milgram des savoirs](#)
- Sheila Khan in *Debate Africano* (RTP África) on 19 September spoke about open science activities of CONCILIARE in a program dedicated to the current challenges in international relations.
🔊 Listen here: [Debate Africano](#)

PAST EVENTS

Lecture on collective memories of colonialism at Catholic University of Leuven

On 29 August 2025, Laurent Licata gave a lecture on collective memories of colonialism, social identities and intergroup relations at the Second Social Identity Summer School 2025, Catholic University of Leuven. He presented the CONCILIARE project, focusing on the research on museums conducted within WP3.

Paradise Talks: And After Independence? From Liberation Struggles to Today's Struggles (*Conversas do Paraíso: e depois da independência? Das lutas da*

libertação às lutas de hoje)

Between 18–20 September 2025, the Paraíso festival brought to Braga, Portugal, a three-day program filled with music, cinema, theatre, and powerful debates. The event celebrated the 50th anniversary of the independences of the Portuguese-speaking African countries across different venues in the city, and resulted from a partnership between CONCILIARE, FazCultura (Municipality of Braga), and other cultural partners: BANTUMEN, gnration, Livraria Centésima Página, Teatro Circo and Braga Public Library.

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UPCOMING EVENTS

WP1 Workshop in Coimbra

On 4–5 December 2025, a workshop will take place at University of Coimbra, bringing together the three WP1 teams from Coimbra University, Helsinki University, and Sapienza University, along with Afropean members and two external experts: Mario Carretero (Professor at Universidad Autónoma de Madrid and coordinator of the research group Think History & Memory) and Karel van Nieuwenhuysse (Associate Professor of History Didactics at Katholieke Universiteit Leuven and coordinator of the Specific History Teacher Training Programme).

The aim is to advance the development of the evidence-based method (TM) focused

on textbooks, which can be recommended to foster confidence in change in CCH by reframing narratives in educational materials.

DELIVERABLES

At the end of August, four deliverables were successfully submitted to the European Commission portal and will soon be available on Zenodo:

- **D2.1:** *Technical report on CCH disputed traces* (WP2)
- **D3.1:** *Report on changes in the exhibition spaces of museums* (WP3)
- **D4.1:** *Report of focus groups findings* (WP4)
- **D6.3:** *Quality Assurance Report* (WP6)

Along with the deliverable submitted in December 2024 — **D1.1:** *Technical report on narratives and images* (WP1) — CONCILIARE now counts on at least one empirical research deliverable from each Work Package.

These milestones reflect the excellent collaborative work carried out over the past months. **Congratulations to the whole team!**

Thank you for your continued support and engagement in CONCILIARE!

Júlia Vilhena, Rosa Cabecinhas, Teresa Forte and Emiliano Abad

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